

Everything we (think we) know about Narrative CVs (NCVs)

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*This is one of three briefings sharing key insights from our work on NCV implementation. This edition is for **organisations considering NCV implementation** for funding allocation, hiring, promotion, or other purposes. The other briefings target organisations already implementing NCVs and meta-researchers studying NCV implementation.*

Overview

This briefing presents insights and recommendations, based on a review of publicly available documents and stakeholder engagement in interviews, focus groups, and workshops.

We explored three questions:

1. How are users reacting to NCVs?
2. Is NCV implementation resulting in intended outcomes and impacts?
3. Are formats and guidance optimal for achieving those outcomes?

Key insights

Our work concludes on the following answers to these questions:

- 1. User reactions:** Evaluations show **broad acceptance of the NCV format across user groups**, with applicants generally more positive than reviewers. **Applicants** value the opportunity to highlight a wider range of contributions, as well as the inclusion of academic age and the flexibility to omit sections (where these features are present). Their main concerns centre on whether reviewers interpret NCVs as intended and whether the format may disadvantage certain groups. **Reviewers** appreciate the more nuanced framing, contextualisation, and emphasis on the significance of contributions, along with the potential to tailor CVs more effectively. Their concerns focus on the challenge of adapting to a new evaluation approach, especially when full publication lists are excluded from application materials.
- 2. Outcomes:** It is too early to tell whether most of the outcomes, particularly the mid- and long-term goals set by organisations who have adopted NCVs, are being fully achieved. What is already evident is that **NCVs enable a focus on broader contributions but their introduction as a standalone intervention does not guarantee changes in which contributions are given recognition, or in who ultimately receives funding**. NCVs are not a silver bullet; many other factors will play into whether anticipated outcomes are realised.
- 3. Guidance and support:** One such factor is the level of support provided to users. While applicants are generally well supported, more attention is needed to the variation in local support, and they would benefit from greater transparency around assessment practices and access to positively evaluated NCV examples. In contrast, **reviewers currently lack sufficient support to help them adapt to a new evaluation approach**. This includes the absence of clear rules and mechanisms to ensure consistent implementation, particularly regarding the use of metrics and other quantitative information, by organisations adopting NCVs. **This gap is a major barrier to achieving NCV-related outcomes, as changes in reviewer behaviour may be the rate-limiting step in the implementation process.**

Recommendations for organisations considering NCV implementation

Based on the full review, we recommend that organisations considering NCV implementation:

- **Determine the rationale for change and NCV suitability** – Whether NCVs are suitable depends on your organisation's aims. The annex outlines common expected outcomes and current evidence on whether they are being achieved. While evidence remains limited, no studies suggest NCV implementation leads us in the wrong direction.
- **Set realistic expectations for what NCVs can achieve and over what timeframe** – NCVs are not a silver bullet: simply replacing traditional CVs won't transform your evaluation. Research on peer review innovations shows that practices are not solely determined by formal tools and evolve gradually as researcher communities adapt.
- **Ensure alignment between NCV principles and evaluation practices** – Misalignment between the rationale for NCV introduction and existing criteria or processes, such as continued emphasis on track record, or panel discussions failing to discourage journal metrics, can undermine implementation. Organisations adopting NCVs should clearly define how metrics and other quantitative information should be used and establish mechanisms to ensure these practices are consistently applied.
- **Engage key communities to support the rationale** – This is critical in institutional contexts. Evidence suggests NCVs may not deliver intended outcomes if those involved in the implementation are not ready to shift focus from traditional indicators, especially when these actors also have full autonomy in how they approach the evaluation. Engagements ideally include discussion of the rationale for introducing NCVs, alongside separate discussions on the practicalities of implementation.
- **Commit resources upfront to support communities through the transition** – This includes support throughout the process for applicants and, crucially, for reviewers, who are often underserved. Reviewer behaviour plays a central role in whether outcomes, envisioned with NCV implementation, can be achieved.

Key opportunity / challenge

Opportunity: Our evidence shows that NCVs offer an opportunity for broader contributions to be recognised in academia, which could contribute to fostering a more people-oriented research culture and to enhancing research quality and impact.

Challenge: However, whether this opportunity is realised depends on practice change by reviewers, as there is a risk that reviewers don't assess the format as intended, and on other evaluation and system-wide measures moving in the same people-oriented direction.

Further background

Several funders and institutions have, over the past decade, piloted a new academic CV format known as the 'Narrative CV' (NCV), which emphasises narrative over itemised lists and allows users to expand beyond the typical career and output milestones usually included in CVs. This shift was driven by concerns about the excessive focus on quantitative criteria in review and hiring panels, often seen to encourage perverse incentives – it is also considered an important tool for virtue signalling towards a better research culture.

The format was introduced with a range of intended outcomes in mind and has since been evaluated through studies focused mainly on user acceptance and experience, as well as changes in CV use and evaluation practices as a result of NCV introduction.

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Annex - Overview of findings for intended outcomes

Outcomes in this overview were consolidated across the studies considered in our review, alongside outcomes captured in the Joint Funders Group & Alternative Uses Group (2023) *Résumé for Research and Innovation (R4RI)-like narrative CV: Shared Evaluation Framework (2.0)*. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8060614>

<p>Streamlining and simplification</p>	<p>Several studies recommend further alignment of NCVs within and between organisations, while noting that this should mean requesting relevant information in the same format, rather than blanket standardisation.</p> <p>Survey data on the time and difficulty of writing or reviewing NCVs show mixed experiences. Applicants often spend more time preparing their first NCV, and reviewers initially find them harder to assess than traditional CVs.</p>
<p>Recognising more diverse contributions</p>	<p>Several studies show that a broader range of outputs and contributions is included in NCVs and is being considered in evaluations, and data across studies confirms users agree the format supports this goal.</p> <p>However, there is limited evidence that this leads to more diverse funding outcomes, at least in the short term. A few studies offer anecdotal examples suggesting the format may benefit a small group of individuals who previously might have been excluded.</p>
<p>Reducing barriers across sectors and disciplines</p>	<p>Data across studies confirms users agree the format supports this goal.</p> <p>Some studies suggest NCVs help shift perceptions of irregular career paths, but workshop participants noted that the NCV, while offering space for the description of competencies, cannot resolve the inherent misalignment between outputs-focused evaluation in academia and competency-focused evaluation in other sectors.</p>
<p>Reducing bias / Supporting EDI</p>	<p>Many studies raise concerns that NCVs may introduce bias, disadvantaging certain groups (e.g. gender, minoritised, English level, writing skills, confidence, institutional support, seniority). One study notes a missed opportunity for NCVs to better support caregivers.</p> <p>Evidence on how bias plays out is limited; one text analysis found language differences by demographics as well as positively evaluated NCVs having distinct language features.</p> <p>Another study found promotional language is rare, and positive language is occasional and does not result in a selection advantage. A challenge consists of a lack of clear definitions of bias in research evaluation more generally, and to establish the extent to which bias can be attributed to NCVs specifically rather than systemic effects.</p>
<p>Driving mindset change and better research culture</p>	<p>A few studies suggest a mindset shift is happening; applicants reflect differently on achievements, and reviewers reconsider the complexity of excellence and rethink how it is assessed, especially when supported throughout the evaluation process. At the same time, several studies show reviewers often continue to rely on traditional, publication-based indicators, with feedback highlighting difficulty evaluating without them.</p> <p>Several studies suggest that introducing NCVs as a standalone intervention is unlikely to lead to meaningful shifts in mindset and culture. Achieving such change requires a broader alignment of other evaluation and organisational measures moving in the same direction.</p>